

Research Article

Marketing of Kolanut (*Cola nitida*) in Sagamu and Ikenne Local Government Areas of Ogun State

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Abstract

Kolanut market is characterized by price fluctuations through space and time in the study areas. This is linked to the large numbers of market intermediaries who acts between the primary producers, middle-men and the consumers. The study was carried out in Sagamu and Ikenne Local Government Areas LGAs of Ogun State. Data was collected using a multi-stage sampling technique by randomly selecting one hundred and twenty (120) respondents in the two (2) LGAs of Ogun State. Structured interview schedule was used as instrument in collecting information on socio-economic characteristics of kolanut marketers; including the cost of pods harvested, processing, packaging, and transportation. The data were analyzed using simple descriptive statistics like means, percentage tabulations, profitability analysis and gross margin; while the constraints were rated on a 4-point Likert type scale to determine their severity. The gross margins of the kolanut products and their profitability analysis were computed using cost and returns analysis. The results revealed that kolanut marketing in the study areas yielded positive outcomes. The study further revealed that majority of the marketers are females (57.50) percent while (42.50) percent were males. The modal group of the marketers was 41-50 years with a mean age of 35. Majority of the marketers had primary education (71.67) percent. The average family size of the marketers is six (6) per households while (66) percent were married. (45.83) percent sourced their fund from personal savings. The study recommended an accelerated improvement in scaling up of marketing of kolanut enterprises and its contribution to the Gross Domestic Product and generation of foreign exchange earnings for the country.

Keywords: kolanut marketing, gross margins, cost and returns, constraints.

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Introduction

After many years of neglects, agriculture is once again seizing the attention of the Nigerian government, entrepreneurs, investors, academia, development donors and farmers as a main driver of the economy. Food security, hunger and poverty alleviation are the key source of every developing nation. The breeze of agricultural transformation coming up in Nigeria will go a long way to a large extent in dependence on value addition, processing, diversification, packaging and marketing options, commercialization of numerous small-scale processors, producers and marketers. The economics of producing both food and industrial products as revealed by Anyaegbunam *et al.*, (2008) is profitable.

Kolanut is an important economic crop in the south-west region of Nigeria. Kolanut is highly produced in Sagamu and Ikenne LGAs of Ogun State and other South-Western States of Nigeria (Ondo, Ekiti, Oyo, Osun) and largely consumed in the Northern part of Nigeria. Kolanut is a tropical tree crop with over 20 species; out of which *Cola nitida* (Gbanja) and *Cola acuminata* (Abata) are the two main species grown in Nigeria. The specie known as *C. nitida* is referred to as “the true kola of commerce” has featured in the internal trade of West Africa for a number of centuries (Nzekwu, 1961; Eijnatten, 1969). Kola is an important economic cash crop to a significant proportion of Nigerian population who are involved in kola farming, industrial utilization, trading and marketing. The place of kola-nut production before the dependence of the economy on petroleum cannot be over emphasized (Akinbode, 1982).

The consumption of *Cola acuminata* is greatly cherished by the Yoruba of south-west and northern part of Nigeria while south-east prefers the *Cola nitida*. The commodity gains very significant attention during marriage and burial ceremonies; and even during everyday entertainment of important visitors where it is offered as valuable gift. In addition to the economic and social importance of kola-nut, it enjoys special favour with the people of northern Nigeria who have accepted *Cola nitida* as a stimulant substitute for alcoholic drinks because of Islamic belief on alcoholic drinks.

Agricultural marketing is the distribution of farm produce from the producer (farmers) down to the final consumer (end-users). Proper marketing of kola nut has the tendency of improving the income of both farmers and the middle men in the distribution channel. Marketing and prices of major agricultural export commodities in Nigeria are subjected to sudden market disruptions that may affect export supply, domestic demands and supply. Kohls (1968) defined marketing as the performance of all business activities

which involved the flow of goods and services from the point of initial agricultural production until they reach the final consumer; while Adegeye and Dittoh (1990) also defined marketing as the activities which aid the movement of commodities from the farm to the consumer; these include assembling of goods, storage, transportation, processing, grading and financing of all these afore-mentioned activities. However, studies have shown that efficient marketing system stimulates agricultural production (Awoyinka and Ikpsi, 2005; Adesope et.al, 2005). Kola nuts are commonly sighted in Nigerian markets, cities and villages. They are often sold by street vendors at bus-stops and train depots. A lot of Nigerian consumes kola nuts regularly, even on daily basis for the medicinal, stimulating and sustaining properties. However, kolanut traders who can understand market structure has his finger on the pulse of the market, and can respond instantly to risk, uncertainties and opportunities in the market as they occur. Kolanut farmers have also been facing a number of challenges in term of production, processing and marketing of kolanut in the state.

There is no standard local price or grading for kolanut in Nigeria, however information on market transaction, especially with reference to price determination, measurement, size of nuts as well as quality of nuts/grading are based on mutual knowledge; understanding of the buyers and sellers, this includes the middlemen. In order to remove this biasness in marketing of kola nut in Nigeria this necessitated for this study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to analyze the marketing of Kolanut in Sagamu and Ikenne Local Government Areas of Ogun State. Other objectives include:

- To describe the socio-economic characteristics of kolanut marketers in Sagamu and Ikenne Local Government Areas of Ogun State;
- To determine the profitability of kolanut marketers in the study areas; and
- To outline the constraints of Kolanut Marketing.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

This study was carried out in Sagamu and Ikenne Local Government Areas of Ogun State, Nigeria. The state has land mass of 16,409.26km². It has a population of 3,728,098 people (National Population Commission, 2006); which has leap-frogged to about 4.5million with over 360,000 farm families. It has a mean annual temperature of 32°C; with a relative humidity (RH) of 95%. The state has 4 Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) zones namely: Abeokuta, Remo, Yewa and Ijebu.

The study areas are located in the tropical rain forest region which is known for the production of tree crops mainly timber, cocoa, kola, citrus, rubber, oil palm, etc. The arable crops grown mostly as mixed crops include maize, yam, cassava, melon, cocoyam, rice, sugar cane and leafy vegetables. The study area is an important commercial and industry area. Apart from agriculture a considerable number of people of Remo-land have shown interest in kolanut trading; daily, periodic and night markets which serves as outlets for agricultural produce and other goods within and outside. The State has 20 Local Government Areas (LGAs) with its administrative capital at Abeokuta. The predominant occupation of the people in Ogun state are farming, hunting, trading, goldsmith, tailoring, oil palm processing, processing and milling of rice, palm wine, weaving, carving, transportation, agro-allied and cement industries, oil and gas and manufacturing companies with over sixty (60) spring-ups industries.

Sampling Techniques/ Analytical Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for this study. In the first stage, two Local Government Areas were randomly selected from Remo (Ikenne) agricultural zone. The second stage involved a random selection of five communities from each of the two LGAs. In the third stage, 6 kolanut farmers were randomly selected from each of the 10 communities; making a total of 120 respondents. Primary data were collected using structured interview schedule as instrument. Ogun State Agricultural Development Programme (OGADEP), Cocoa Research Institute of Nigeria (CRIN) Ibadan, Journals, Agricultural Development Programme (ADP)/Extension Agents, Research reports, Publications, Proceedings and market surveys provided the sampling frame while others were administered from the instruments of the kolanut farmers and marketers. Data captured in the interview schedule covered socio-economic characteristics of kolanut farmers, cost of kolanut production per bag (including marketing inputs, labour, processing, preservation, packaging, storage, grading and transportation, etc) and the revenue generated from sales of kolanut. Ten (10) constraints to kolanut marketing were identified and captured. The data collected were subjected to simple descriptive statistics like mean, frequency, tabulation and percentages. The profit margin was calculated using the Brown model (1979) which states that;

$$GM = TR - TVC$$

Where,

GM = Gross Margin

TR = Total Revenue

TVC = Total Variable Cost

The constraints to marketing of kolanut were rated on a 4-point Likert type scale to determine their severity. It should be noted that most farm lands are displayed for kolanut production (assemblage), processing and marketing were acquired through family inheritance and rentage. Fixed costs of simple farm tools (cutlasses, go-to-hell, baskets, etc.) and replacement were negligible to the extent that they can be ignored when estimating profitability of small scale enterprises Olukosi and Erhabor, (1988).

Results and Discussion

The summary statistics of socio-economic variables involved in Kola-nut marketing were presented in the Table 1.

Table 1 Socio-Economic Variables of Kolanut Marketers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
<20	3	2.50
21 - 30	6	5.00
31 - 40	30	25.00
41 - 50	42	35.00
>50	39	3.50
Total	120	100
Mean = 35yrs		
Gender		
Male	51	42.50
Female	69	57.50
Total	120	100
Marital status		
Single	10	8.30
Married	79	65.80
Widowed	23	19.20
Divorced	8	6.70
Total	120	100
Educational status		
No formal education	18	15.00

Primary education	86	71.67
Secondary education	14	11.67
Tertiary education	2	1.67
Total	120	100
Experience in marketing (years)		
<5	6	5.00
6-9	65	54.17
>10	49	40.83
Total	120	100
Household size (No of Family size)		
1 - 4	7	5.83
5 -12	72	60.00
>12	41	34.16
Total	120	100
Source of funds		
Personal savings	55	45.83
Money lenders	23	19.17
Cooperative group/societies	26	21.67
Bank loan	10	8.33
Others	6	5.00
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey (2008).

Table 1 revealed that the mean age of the respondents was 35 years with most (35.00 percent) within the productive age range of 41-50 years. Table 1 also showed that kolanut marketing is carried out by both gender with majority of them (57.5 percent) being females. Almost 66 percent of them are married. Furthermore, Table 1 showed that 71.7 percent of the marketers had primary education with only 2 percent having tertiary education.

The marketing experience of the farmers is between 6 and 9 years. Sixty (60.0) percent of the household size is between 5 and 12. Majority of the farmers (45.83 percent) sourced their funds through personal savings while 8 percent sourced their loans funds through commercial banks. Kolanut marketers interviewed attributed this to the high interest rates charged by the commercial banks and the stringent conditionality required for accessing bank loans.

Table 2 Cost and Returns Analysis of Kolanut Marketers

ITEMS/VARIABLES	NO OF PERSON/₦	UNIT	TOTAL COST (₦)	PERCENTAGE (%)
(a) Fixed Cost			₦ 11,800	10.92
(b) Variable Cost				
Harvesting	10 × ₦ 800	(Man days)	₦ 8,000	7.40
Processing	10 × ₦ 800	"	₦ 8,000	7.40
Marketing	5 × ₦ 900	"	₦ 4,500	4.16
Labour	12 × ₦ 800	"	₦ 9,600	8.88
Transportation	2 × ₦ 1,200	"	₦ 2,400	2.22
Packaging Material (leaves, papers)	10 × ₦ 4,500	"	₦ 45,000	41.63
Grading/packaging	8 × ₦ 800	"	₦ 6,400	5.92
Storage	8 × ₦ 800	Man days	₦ 6,400	5.92
Agro-chemicals	6 × ₦ 1000	Litres	₦ 6,000	5.55
TOTAL REVENUE			₦ 108,100.00	

Source: Field survey (2008).

Total cost - Total revenue = ₦108,100 - ₦11,800 = ₦96,300.00

Table 2 revealed the total variable cost (TVC) of ₦108,100.00 while the fixed cost is ₦11,800. Therefore, the Gross margin of kolanut marketing in the study areas is moderately profitable, with highest profit recorded ₦96,300.00; (Benefit/Cost ratio of 9.16) which shows that for every ₦9, there was a return of ₦0.16 (16 kobo) on investment.

Table 3: Analysis of Constraints to Kolanut Marketing/ Marketers (N=120)

S/ N	Constraints	4 Very severe	3 Severe	2 Not severe	1 Indiffere nt	Σ	\bar{x}	Ran k	Remark s
1	High Transportati on Cost	28(23. 3)	80(66. 7)	7(5.83)	5(4.2)	37 1	3.0 9	1	Very Severe
2	Poor Rural Infrastructur e	35(29. 2)	60(50)	22(18. 3)	3(2.5)	36 7	3.0 5	4	Severe
3	Lack of Fund (Credit)	72(60)	20(16. 7)	27(22. 5)	1(0.83)	40 3	3.3 6	3	Very Severe
4	Poor Storage Facilities	61(50. 8)	40(33. 3)	14(11. 7)	5(4.2)	39 7	3.3 1	2	Very Severe
5	Inconsistent in Government Policies	50(41. 7)	30(25)	28(23. 3)	12(10)	35 8	2.9 8	6	Severe
6	Poor Pricing for Products	16(13. 3)	91(75. 8)	11(9.2)	2(1.7)	36 1	3.0 0	5	Severe
7	Poor Extension Services	20(16. 7)	50(41. 7)	42(35)	8(6.70)	32 2	2.6 8	9	Not Severe
8	Pests and Diseases	18(15)	31(25. 8)	58(48. 3)	13(10.83)	29 4	2.4 5	10	Not Severe
9	Poor Marketing for Kolanut Products	48(40)	19(15. 8)	43(35. 8)	10(8.3)	34 5	2.8 7	7	Severe
10	High Cost of Labour	42(35)	5(4.2)	69(57. 5)	4(3.33)	32 5	2.7 0	8	Not Severe

Source: Field Survey (2008). Parentheses are in percentage.

Table 3 shows analysis of the severity of constraints to kolanut marketing in the study area using a 4-point Likert-type scale. It was computed by summing the scores (frequency multiplied by magnitude of constraints and determine the mean (\bar{x}) which were then ranked. Results in table 3 revealed that lack of credit, non-availability of loan,

high cost of transportation and storage facilities fall in the category of “very severe” with respective mean score of 3.36, 3.31 and 3.09. availability of storage facilities and poor road network with respective mean scores of 3.06 and 3.01 were in the category of “severe”, while high cost of labour, grading, packaging and processing of kolanut and poor prices of products were considered “not severe” with mean scores of 2.99, 2.88 and 2.71 respectively. The response regards impact of extension services in table 3 poses a surprise as extension farmer’s ratio in Nigeria is noted to be as high as 1:2,500 (Ilevbaoje, 2004). Perhaps, the kolanut marketers (farmers) may have underestimated the importance of extension in increasing their production, processing, packaging, grading and marketability. A similar surprise was also expressed by the response of the kolanut farmers (marketers) regarding availability of grading, packaging, processing and marketing pattern, as most farmers/marketers interviewed sourced their products locally (unimproved/less graded/packages). This however, has negative implications on quality of kola nut marketing.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Limitless opportunities exist for kolanut as a cash crop for addressing food security enhancing rural and foreign income. There are prospects for high revenue generation and profitability if the packaging, processing and marketing patterns of kolanut is upgraded, productivity are increased and scale of operation expanded to meet the global competitiveness.

The findings of this study showed that;

- a. Marketing of kolanut enterprises in study areas engaged fairly literate farmers (71%) of both gender.
- b. Most farmers (kolanut marketers) are in the active productive age bracket of between 40 and 50 years above.
- c. Kolanut marketing enterprises are faced with ‘very severe’ constraints; high transport cost, non-availability of/ poor storage facilities and lack of credit.

To mitigate the constraints identified in the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Kolanut marketers should be encouraged to access micro-credit in order to increase their scale of operation (marketing).
2. Government and non-governmental organizations should boost extension delivery in order to increase uptake and utilization of high yielding varieties of kolanut production, processing, packaging, storage, grading in other to make kolanut marketing more attractive at the international market.

3. Government should put in place sustainable buy-back policy that will encourage kolanut production, processing, grading, storage, price stabilization and marketing.
4. Kolanut marketers should be encouraged to form themselves into viable cooperative groups or associations in order to facilitate access to farm inputs, marketing innovations, grading and micro-credit or loans facilities.

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